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The Media as a Political Resource in Nigeria: A Rear-View Mirror

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Abstract

In virtually all climes and regions of the world, the mass media in all guises is a political resource. The paper explores the public goals which the media can be used to serve. Most especially national integration and political education in a plural and deeply divided society like Nigeria coupled with her babel of voices that hinders the media to wear the toga of national outlook. The paper also took a dim view of functions of the mass media in the society cum the traditional and constitutional roles of the fourth estate of the realm. Attention was also paid to the historical metamorphosis of the mass media in Nigeria. The paper however infers that the many 'sins' of the media as highlighted in the piece must be taken care of to enhance developmental journalism.

KEYWORDS: Mass Media, Democracy, Resource, 'Sins', Watchdog.

First Words:

The press...qualifies as one of the many invisible governments. The Press is capable of making or destroying governments given appropriate conditions; it can cause war or create difficulties (Kennet Kaunda, 1968 cited in Tusa, 1992).

No doubt, the mass media from ages is a political resource. More so, that there are public interest political goals which the media can be used to serve. Such goals include the following: information to the public, public enlightenment, social criticism and exposing governmental

arbitrariness, national integration and political education (Onyeoziri, 1982) It is imperative to emphasise the fact that fundamental to the canons of democracy is the idea of participation by the people in the polity. This could be in three dimensions viz: (a) periodic selection or election (b) routine involvement and (c) public opinion on issues and event of the day. Thus, democratic development involves a widening of the public sphere such that in the words of Williams Gamson “public discourse empowers citizens, given their voice and agency, builds community and engages citizens in the democratic process through their active participation in public sphere” (Olukotun, 2018:13).

Be that as it is, the media is critical in enhancing democratic participation at all levels of democratization viz: (a) information sharing (b) democratic consultation (c) decision-making and (d) initiating actions. In essence, the media is a political resource which if not well handled could be dysfunctional to democracy also. One can easily recall that one issue that came up in the now historic Aburi meeting of the defunct Supreme Military Council (SMC) was the role of the Nigerian Press in provoking the crisis that culminated into the 30-month agonizing Civil War between 1967 and 1970. The media blew the crisis between the Federal Government and the Biafran side beyond proportion through needless sensationalism. Whereas, the media ought to play the role of mechanism of national integration in a deeply divided and plural society like Nigeria. Aside from the negative functions, one of the more common political uses which the media is put is that of moulding the citizens’ perception of political reality in line with the preferences of the political leadership (Onyeoziri, 1982); currently the media convey to the authorities the grievances, needs, problems, hopes and aspirations of the people too. In that respects, the media can thus make up the major deficiency of indirect or representative democracy (Ojo, 2013:429-438). Rather than the elitist posture of the media in Nigeria that reports mainly government activities and top elites in the society. The common-man no doubt is far from being news worthy. They are mentioned only in case of disasters and figure of casualties without mentioning of their names.

Conversely, the media conveys to the authorities, the grievances, the needs, the problems, the hopes and aspirations of the people, and the responses of the authorities may in turn be conveyed by the media to the people too. In that respect, the media can thus make up the major deficiency of indirect or representative democracy. In the same vein and as a corollary to the latter, the media can also act as a day-to-day parliament of the people, which may be more effective than the actual parliament. Furthermore, the media can perform the task of the watchdog of the people's interests. The media can expose the corruption, waste, inefficiency and negligence on the part of the authorities. Through investigative journalism, scams and scandals can be unearthed, anti-social activities exposed and implementation of the policies and programmes monitored. The mass media can thus act as an ombudsman on behalf of the people almost every day (Sawant, 2009:9-11).

Perhaps it is worth reinstating again that the mass media whether print or electronic in a democratic polity like Nigeria plays three important roles viz:

- (a) They inform citizens on matters of public policy and politics by presenting and debating alternatives;
- (b) They act as watchdog by uncovering political, economic and corporate corruptions as well as other forms of abuses of power or inept policies also;
- (c) The media helps empower citizens to be aware and vigilant of civil and political rights and how to exercise these rights (see, Nigeria Freedom of Expression Community advertorial, in *Tell*, September, 20, 2004:47) Lagos.

Through the aforementioned roles, media help to build and sustain a participatory, transparent and accountable governance structure. It is in view of the foregoing imperative roles of the media that John Tusa, a veteran journalist and a one-time Managing Director of the British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) world service, London, avers that:

Free press is essential to a healthy democracy; indeed it is a condition of it; governments and journalists have different objectives and that tension between them is inevitable (1992).

In a comprehensive way, Ralph Akinfeleye (2003:31) – a doyen of media study - highlighted the basic imperatives of the press in the promotion and preservation of national interest and sustainable democracy thus:

- Common carrier of ideas;
- Representative picture of the society;
- Truth and meaning of truth in a democracy;
- Classification of the values and goals of the society;
- Uncover and never to cover-up;
- Make the government accountable to the people;
- Inform, educate and entertain the people;
- Promote the concept of accountability, integrity, honesty, fairness and equity;
- Give voice to the voiceless in the society;
- Society agenda-setter;
- Forging national unity and integration;
- Promotion of society cultures, and the moral value system;
- Promotion of sustainable national interest at all times;
- Promotion of journalistic integrity (the journalists should now promote themselves from being called ‘Press boys’ to be called **THE PRESS EXECUTIVES** or the captains of the Fourth Estate of the Realm.

This paper is organized into some sections with the above introductory overview which details the functions of the mass media along with its nexus with democracy. The second part takes a cursory look at the mass media as the fourth estate of the realm. Part three briefly sketch the evolution of the media from the ancient, medieval and contemporary times most especially in Africa. Part four however juxtaposes the current media landscape with the past noting the many ‘sins’ of the

contemporary mass media. The paper however infers that practitioners need to imbibe the ethos of the profession to achieve developmental journalism.

II. The Fourth Estate of the Media: Traditional and Constitutional Functions

The idea of the fourth estate of the media emanates from the insightful work of Montesquieu's work – *The Spirit of the Laws* which argues that freedom is not possible where the powers of the state are not kept strictly separated (see, Montesquieu, 1748 cited in Ojo, 2018:49); leading to the media themselves being designated as another power, namely, the fourth power, aligned with executive, legislative and judicial powers of the state. In effect, referring to the media as the Fourth Estate, Fourth Power, or Watchdog vis-à-vis the institutions of the State has promoted “press freedom as a corporate right” over “individual freedom” and focuses, on the media's relationship with other arms of the State when, in fact:

Mass communication obviously involves wider areas of competing Interests and powers...(including): 1 media owners' interest in using their Media as a means of self-expression and profit maximization, (2) the general Interest of capital to advertise commodities on an even larger scale, (3) Demand from audiences for media use... (4) various civil society groups (5) a General (ethnic) interest in maintaining the rights of all citizens and in Media performing their public service functions (cited in Splichael, 2002:5-26).

In essence, the potent body of ideas on the media and politics describes the media in terms of:

The Fourth Estate, Fourth Power and Watchdog, often used as Nicknames for the mass media, which suggest that social functions of the Media

refer to the exercise of power and control in society, (and) reflect The general significance of the relationship between (political) power And the media (see, Splichael, 2002 cited in Agbaje, Idowu, Agbade and Layade, (2014:325-345).

In virtually all human collectivises, the role of the mass media – print and electronic – public or private ones are similar inclusive of the ‘new media’. The nature and form of government only condition the extent to which the roles are performed from one polity to the other (Ojo, 2006). Nana Konadu Aggeman Rawlings, former First lady of Ghana was unequivocal when she noted that “the state-owned media are supposed to support the government, because they are paid from government resources (Temin and Smith, 2012:585). This is a warped view of the media by those in positions of authority. This perception makes government owned media outfits not to be trusted during elections because they are known to be reckless government megaphones. While Kofi Annan, Secretary General, United Nations, speaking on the media, on the other hand, he said inter alia “...the media must actively seek truth in the public’s behalf and be free to tell it as they see it” (ibid.). Audience of the mass media expects different things based on their position in the society. This is not unconnected with the fact that “the mass media have come largely to determine the cognitive and affective perceptions of the non-vocal world through their portrayals of events issues, people and places (Ibid.).

Furthermore, the Fourth Estate of the Realm, that is the Press, whether print or electronic, is an essential element of a democracy as earlier emphasized. It has three main purposes: it informs, it educates and it entertains and all good media must be seen to be performing these three functions. It must not be inhibited in the performance of those functions in a democratic setting. Hence, the laws of the country and the editorial policy evolved by the proprietors must facilitate the performance of those functions in a democratic setting. Hence, the laws of the country and the editorial policy evolved by the proprietors must facilitate the performance of those functions. But the freedom of the press is freedom

under the law. It is not about lawlessness, but the law itself must be sane and reasonable as well as justifiable in a democratic society for it to be obeyed.

Meanwhile, two things regulate the conduct of the press. The first one is the law of the country, both the letters and the spirit of the law. By the letters of the law we mean the clauses of the totality of the constitution of the country as well as all those laws which are validly passed or made by the country as well as all those laws which are validly passed or made by the legislature of the country. The media however, must be politically responsible as patriotic estate of the country (Adebanwi, 2004:763a). They are not expected to say or write those things which affect the National Interest adversely. While the National Interest of a country does not have to be coterminous with the interest of the leaders at all times.

Nonetheless, just as we talk about the doctrine of Separation of Powers, the media must also be seen to be separate from the other three arms of government, that is, the Executive, the Legislature and the Judiciary (Ojo, 2018, 49-62). Government must not interfere with the operations of the press as long as the press obeys the laws of the land. But the laws of the land are not the pleasure of individuals or a group or a clique. Whenever the press contravenes the law, it must be dealt with following the due process of the law and this implies: (a) that the judge is not the accuser; (b) that the charge against the press must be put clearly and unambiguously (c) that the accused must be given an opportunity as well as the facility to defend itself and (d) that there must be a neutral arbiter which must be a third party these are the basic canons of the principle of the Rule of Law in any democratic society. It is also the responsibility of practitioners to abide strictly by the editorial policy of their Newspapers or broadcast outfits, while the editorial policy must also comply with both the letters and the spirit of the law. For a country that opts for a democratic system, the editorial policy must also further enhance the deepening of the democratic system.

This section will be incomplete without noting the fact that political elites in all regions and climes of the world do aspire to manipulate the

Fourth Estate of the realm. They do this in a number of ways: (1) they deliberately distort the information they disseminate to their audience, the citizens; (2) they knowingly exclude some critical pieces of information, especially if those pieces are likely to lead the citizens into drawing a conclusion that the leadership does not favour; (3) they can remain simply quiet over some crucial issues where the population is thirsting for information; and (4) they seek to divert the people's attention from very important issues by crowding the people's mind with trivialities (Ojo, 2003:821-840). They can couple these with trying to prevent opposition elite groups from acquiring control of some mass media for fear that those media could be used to neutralize the government's political control efforts (Ibid.).

In an insightful speech, Awolowo (of blessed memory), enumerated and emphasize three important characteristics which the Press appears to have acquired in the course of its evolution. Firstly, the Press, apart from being a disseminator of news, is the most potent medium by means of which the masses of people ventilate their feelings and views on any issue of the day. Secondly, and in consequences of the first characteristic, the Press has always been and still is inseparably identified with the masses. Lastly the freedom of the Press is no more and no less than the liberty of the citizen. In other words, the measure of the liberty of the Press is the quantum of freedom enjoyed by the citizen, and vice versa (Awolowo, 1958).

III. Evolution of the Media

The evolution of the mass media could be traced to three stages: (i) Oral tradition (ii) Print era and (iii) Electronic dispensation with technological advancement. The first stage encompasses all human societies. It was an era of face-to-face and storytelling mostly by travellers. It was prevalent in Africa when town criers would go to the market places to announce to the traders and travellers the decision of the Monarch or Ruler on any issue that concern all. The major advantage of this 'crude' method of political communication was immediate feedback whereby the audience reacts by telling the town crier that they heard him and that he should tell the King their

compliance or otherwise of the information passed across to them. In case of curfew for ritual purposes or other festivities, the announcement of the town crier would be communicated down to villages and hamlets why they should not go out on any specific day for ritual purposes or festivities. However this mode of communication was possible only in micro societies with population sizes being small. No doubt, before the advent of newspapers, the dissemination of news had to be done by word of mouth. This was by its very nature extremely slow and narrowly circumscribed. The news which was transmitted from mouth to mouth was more often grossly distorted. One important feature of oral news was that it was transient and impermanent. Consequently, it is comparatively ineffective. It must be pointed out in this connection however, that oral news could be effective in a most dangerous sense. False rumours passed on from mouth to mouth, and distorted and exaggerated in the process of transmission could be the precursor of grave situations and consequences (Awolowo, 1958). Whereas, in modern time, population sizes of some villages makes it extremely impossible for that kind of communication system. This was a replica of the ancient Greek city-states that gave room for direct system of democracy.

We need to emphasize that informal channels of communication are remarkably pervasive and effective in Africa. In road journeys to and from the capital city, drivers and passengers are usually treated to rumours and latest news items in the system that has been variously labeled as the 'bush telegraph', 'side walk radio', or 'pavement radio'. Markets and beer parlors are other important centres for the dissemination of rumours and other informal political messages in Africa (Young, 1984). Despite the distortions inherent in informal flows, such flows provide rural as well as urban citizens in Africa with a far more sophisticated understanding of politics than they might attain if they relied solely on official information. Moments of political tension and crisis often lead to an intensification of informal information flows. In such moments, the official media are often silent either because they do not wish to draw attention to the tensions or

because they are uncertain about how the information concerned should be presented to the public (Ellis, 1989).

With the evolution of modern nation-states coupled with massive human population, development gave way for evolution of the print media. Ever since the beginning of modern press in Belgium in the early 16th century (see, Dare, 1997:535), mass media metamorphosed and graduated to print with newspapers and newsmagazines as we know it in our contemporary time.

In Nigeria, the historical metamorphosis could be traced to 1859 when Rev. Henry Townsend, a missionary of the Church Missionary Society (C.M.S.), established the first Newspaper in Nigeria. It was called *Iwe Irohin Fun Ara Egba ati Yoruba* (meaning, newspaper for the Egba People and the Yoruba) in Abeokuta, Ogun state, the stated objective was 'to beget the habit of seeking information by reading' (Adebanwi, 2004b). Another missionary who contributed to the development of the press in Nigeria was Rev. Hope Waddell, who arrived Calabar in 1846. He came with a printing press and by 1802 had set up the Calabar observer, later with his team he set up *Unwana Efik* in 1885 and *Obupong Efik* in 1886 (Ibid.). This dovetailed into the development of Nationalist Newspapers starting with the Lagos Observer (1882), The Eagle and Lagos Critic (1983), The Mirror (1887), Lagos Echo (1890), Lagos Standard (1885), Lagos Weekly Record (1908), Lagos Daily News (1925), and the Times (1926) (Sunday, 2008).

Until the beginning of the Second Republic in 1979 ownership of electronic media became fairly liberalized when state governments were constitutionally allowed to set up their own broadcast outfits. Hitherto, electronic media was an exclusive preserve of the Federal Government with the fear that they could be abused going by the state of national integration subsequent to the civil strife which ended in 1970. This development also opened a flood gate of private ownership of electronic media too. Since then mass media has been growing in leaps and bound in Nigeria. Presently, of all countries in Africa, Nigeria has boisterous media with many print and electronic media outfits with diverse ownerships including the new media.

IV. ‘SINS’ OF THE MEDIA

In contemporary Nigeria, the mass media has been unable to prevent maladies that are unethical which were not found in the ancient method of communication. But the problems are tied to modern societies. In the words of Ralph Akinfeleye (2004) – a doyen of mass communication – if the state is underdeveloped the media cannot transcend and grow beyond such under-developed or a slowly developing society like ours. For instance large chunk of the segment of the Nigerian media are well known for irresponsible journalism, sensationalism and unethical practices which if not checked may lead the fourth estate of the realm to metamorphose into the fourth estate of the wreck. He puts it pointedly thus:

A nation that is socially responsible in concept, structure, ideology and governance, its press would tend to be responsible in their practice of the profession of journalism. But on the other hand, a national that is socially irresponsible, its journalists would be contaminated with irresponsible instincts and thus would practice irresponsible journalism, sensationalism, bias, outright lies, propaganda journalism and unethical practice which if not quickly checked may, lead the fourth estate of the realm to metamorphose into the fourth estate of the wreck (Akinfeleye, 2008).

Explaining why the media in Nigeria at times do perform undemocratic roles, Olatunji Dare – a veteran – was of the view that “these are not best of times for the Nigerian Press. The inflation and declining purchasing power and disarticulated economy have turned the press into an industry in distress.” (Dare, 2006:22). It is equally for this reason that Nigerian mass media has fallen into the trap of let-them-pay syndrome (LTP). In this LTP concept, truth as the basis of effort and responsible journalism was thrown out and the lure for overt and covert advertising revenue and brown envelopes became the order of the day. This has encouraged misdirection of the crusading spirit of journalism

compounded by the character of the crusaders who are not only poorly trained and poorly paid but also largely inexperienced. It is an embarrassing fact that several media houses hardly pay their staff regularly and it is a notorious fact too that many people in the newsroom today are lacking in experience and exposure. Olukotun puts it more succinctly thus:

As at February 2008 various newspapers, state-owned and private, are owing their staff several months of salary, ranging from three months to 12 months as a result of the distress in that sector of the economy (Olukotun, 2009:13).

One senior journalist observed correctly further that:

The Nigerian journalist goes out to work, armed minimally. Despite today's electronic age. Side by side with his foreign counterpart he is equipped like a stone age communicator. Amidst the cluster of sophisticated gadgetry presided over by His Japanese equivalent. Under these conditions, the Nigerian Journalist is an unsung hero, deplorable low wages and delayed salary payments are common (cited in Olukotun, 2009:13).

It is unfortunate that with Nigeria marking her 25th anniversary of democracy, due to the inclement economy, many media institutions have been forced to abandon their gadfly and watchdog functions, choosing to sing the praises of government and its officials for often inconsequential achievements just to secure advert patronage to shore up income amid bleeding overhead costs that have forced quire a number of retrench staff, fold up or adopt unethical and exploitative means in order to keep in business (see, Yemi Bankole, 2024:25-28). Lanre Arogundade (Newspeak, September, 2024) a media development specialist and Director, International Press Centre, however, opined that the media has not done too badly in the incumbent democratic experience. "The major contributions of the media and civil society

organizations to how the fourth Republic has fared have been in seeking to uphold accountability and transparency in governance particularly in the context of curbing corruption. In this regard the media has unveiled many acts of malfeasance by public office holders, notably a former Speaker of the House of Representatives who forged his educational qualifications” (cited in *Newspeak*, September, 2024:27, Ibadan). Adding that the media even needs to be pitied as it faces barrage of attacks and violation of journalists’ right in their efforts to defend and uphold democracy and rule of law in the country.

The snag however is that the media are often caught in the very contradictions that they pin-point, chief among them corruption, ethnicity, political partisanship and ideological narrowness. A recent *Washington Post* report pin-points the society-wide nature of corruption when it said:

Police call it a *kolanut*, journalists call it the brown Envelope and politician call it welfare package whatever the name, the almighty bribe has long lubricated the Nigerian Society as it has a few others on earth (cited in Olukotun, 2009:13; Smith, 2007)

In a special report by *Tell magazine* entitled “Corruption in the Media”, the magazine reported that *TIME*, the international magazine published a story on Nigeria, alleging that the Federal Ministry of Information offered foreign journalists about \$400 (US dollars) each as inducement. The story went on to explore the thriving brown envelope tradition, concluding that “cash-filled envelopes are routinely handed out by government officials, oil companies, banks and just about anyone else giving a press conference” (*Tell magazine*, May 6 2002, Lagos).

Like *TIME* magazine alleged in its story, it is now the tradition to give ‘brown envelopes’, ‘*keske*’ ‘*communique*’, ‘*handshakes*’ as bribes are jokingly called by journalists at any function. It does not matter whether the function is called by government, corporate firms or even Church events. Aside from this it has also become customary for state

governors to call different categories of Editors together periodically when elections are knocking at the door to offer them '*keske*' so that they can continue to receive favourable press coverage (Author, 2003 see also Author & Adebayo, 2013). The special report equally revealed that when Bisi Akande, was the governor of Osun State, he cried out about the blacking-out of his government's activities for refusing to pay journalists in Osogbo the state capital, monthly stipend like his predecessors were doing. Akande said few weeks after he assumed office, a voucher reached his table for the payment of journalists. He soon learnt that each journalist in the state was on the payroll of the state government. The governor put a stop to it. That step irked the journalists who refused to report any achievement of his administration (see Ojo, 2006:18-19).

In the same vein, one other problem with the media is reckless sensationalism of news coverage, features, editorial and even placement of pictures. For instance, how does one professionally explain headlines such as: 'Rivers of Blood' (The Sun, 8th June, 2006, Lagos). Other examples as noted by Akinfeleye in his inaugural lecture are: (a) 'Islamisation of Zamfara a Reality', (b) OPC vs Ijaw Youth claims five (c) Zamfara Governor dares Obasanjo, (d) Yoruba and Ijaw in Ethnic Violence (e) Oodua Republic Imminent – Igbo should ask for Biafra – OPC chieftain, among others (Akinfeleye, 2003:31).

For instance, in 2008, the International Press Centre, a media resource Centre in Lagos, commissioned a Report on media coverage of three significant issues: development, democratic institutions and governance. Using four national media, **The Guardian**, **The Tribune**, **Champion** and **Daily Trust**, the Centre reviewed the coverage of the issues in November 2008 and came to the conclusion that matters of development took the back seat (Adebisi, 2009). The report confirmed widespread perception that the media pays more attention to governance than development issues. It found that the four media devoted 52% of their attention to governance, leaving 28% for development and 20% for democratic institutional issues. In fact, in terms of space allocation 86% went to governance while a paltry 15% was devoted to

development-related issues (Ibid.). For instance, 68.04% of the stories in the month under review were sourced from government while expert opinion formed the basis of 4%. The man in the street provided information in 6.35% of the stories (Ibid). The situation is far from being cheering now more so with the high rate of illiteracy coupled with parlous state of the economy that makes cover price of national daily unaffordable thereby completely killing the week news magazines on the news stand.

Similarly, the character and commercial disposition of the owner, what is popularly known in media parlance as ownership influence is another kettle of fish. Most of the media proprietors have turned politicians with their individual political leanings and biases. Those that are not politicians are regular callers at the corridors of power seeking one favour or the other. Thus, to balance truth, objectivity and profit making is a dilemma of sort in Nigeria. For instance, in a nascent democracy, where business elite who own media houses still rely on the state for financial and political patronage and considerable number of media houses (most especially) electronic ones wholly owned by the government, does not augur well for the polity. The pattern of media ownership for now promotes irresponsible journalism and not the journalist alone per se (see, Akinfeleye, 2003).

Nonetheless, some journalists think the press have no responsibility whatsoever to the authorities. Whereas, each of us owes duties to the state because it is the state which defines and sustains our rights through the laws of the country. And it demands our loyalty because through the armed forces and the police among others, it alone can defend us from invasion or anarchy. It is for this reason that Lord Annan, the distinguished British academic who was the chairman of the official enquiry into broadcasting in the United Kingdom in March 1977, emphasized the onus on the powerful media, radio and television thus:

...Broadcasters owe a duty to the state, broadcasters should Remember that they owe a duty to the reputation of politicians...statements which discredit not merely the politician but the

whole concept of government without which a society cannot exist, destroy public confidence in the nation in a peculiarly poisonous way. (Tusa, 1992:16)

This destructive role not unconnected with the jaundice perception of media functions by the journalists who erroneously believe that they can operate as a law court trying politicians and other public office holders by holding them into ransome. Thereby taking one the role of another realm of the estate i.e. the judiciary. For Akinfeleye (2003), the press is not cannot be court of law. Adjudication is not part of the constitutional role of the press. Therefore, let us leave the aspect to the other realm which is the court of the land. “Our role is to watchdog, and check-on, gate-keep to uncover and never to cover-up” (Tusa, 1992). No wonder, the media is more personality focused than issues in Nigeria. This is indeed antithetical to positive media role in a democratic polity. The implication of such a media which runs down politicians is simply contaminating public perception of the politicians and when this is persistently done government runs into serious legitimacy crisis (Ojo, 2003). The concomitant effect is what Claude Ake (of blessed memory) calls “governmental instability” (Ake, 1998:28-33). This can tinker with the mentality of the citizens to prefer military autocracy to civil rule.

Moreover, where national interest is not uppermost in the mind of journalists, media roles become dysfunctional in a nascent democracy. In developing societies like Africa, the media needs to be ever conscious not to truncate the process of national integration, cum the safety of lives and properties. Irresponsible journalism can step-up the tempo of irredentist claims in a plural and ethnically divided society like Nigeria; just as it can result into an external invasion too. Two examples readily come to mind. During the Nigeria/Cameroon Bakassi border dispute the, Nigerian media was unable to discern between mere reportage and national interest. Classified documents that were to be used for the defence of Nigeria’s national interest in International Court of Justice (IJC) were published with reckless abandonment (see Ojo,

2004). Secondly, any time ethnic-religious conflict between and among ethnic groups occur, the way and manner headlines are cast usually wear the toga of incitement. A media like this is in fact dangerous to the political health and stability of the state cum national integration. It is not unconnected with these undemocratic roles that successive governments in Nigeria have been weary of granting absolute press freedom to the media. It is however apt to conclude this section of the paper vis-à-vis the danger of uncontrolled media with the position of William H. Thomas, former Editor of the New York Times, who noted that the one thing the press covers more poorly today than anything else is the press itself. He added:

We don't tell our readers/viewers or listeners what we do or how we do it. We don't even admit our mistakes unless we are virtually forced to under threat of court action, advertiser, public opinion or public embarrassment. We do not attempt to explain our problems, our decisions, our news coverage and presentation, our fallibility, our procedures of monitoring governance and making them acceptable to the public. Yet we try to put corrupt public officers on trial (cited in Tusa, 1992).

Perhaps the performance of the mass media in developing countries of the third world may not be better-off until there is a kind of internal mechanism for self-examination objectively is put in place rather than state clampdowns.

Concluding Remarks

The observable problems of the mass media in Nigeria are of great concern to media scholars, practitioners and policy makers alike. The highlighted 'sins' of the media can be summarized in the words of Ayo Olukotun (of blessed memory) thus: 'planted stories', 'spin', 'commercially driven', 'fiction writing,' 'partisan driven' and 'elegantly served nonsense' masquerading as informed commentary have become

the order of the day. Politicians long caricatured by a hostile media or denied the rights of reply are forced to state their cases in paid advertisements, or found their own newspapers or Radio/Television stations or simply carry on with their work hoping that orchestrated bad press will not count vis-à-vis their political fortune (Olukotun, 2009).

Finally, Nigeria requires an investigative oriented media, rather than one that is merely rascally and corrupt. It is an investigative oriented media that can at best transform into a development focused one. This is where the Guild of Editors – Senior cadre journalists – should be a role model for their younger ones. While journalists working with government owned media outfits both print and electronic should be much more attuned to the ethics of their profession. This is because they are ready tools in the hands of governing elite to turn government owned media houses to their megaphones and mouthpieces while in most cases they completely alienated the opposition elements from gaining access to the use of the media most especially electronic ones (see, Ojo & Adebayo, 2013). One cannot lose sight of the fact that modern journalism entails training and re-training more so in the face of evolving Information Technology (ICT) on daily basis. The literate of today may become an illiterate tomorrow if care is not taken. The journalists of analogue era have faded away for good. The *fad* now is to aspire to be able to cope with modern trends in the industry with the use of ICT and strict adherence to the professional etiquette for the good of the industry. No doubt, on their part, journalists must look inwards and self-reform to ensure best professional and ethical practices in the industry (Ojo, 2024:28 cited in *Newspeak*, September, 2024, Ibadan). Currently, it is an all-comer profession that school leavers jump into without the required training. One cannot lose sight of the fundamental problem of poor circulation faced by the print media in Nigeria occasioned by low literacy level. For instance, Punch newspaper editorial of 2023, stated that 31% of Nigerians are illiterates with millions of children out of school. This is a serious challenge to the print media compounded with the distressed economy (see, Olatubosun, 2024).

References

- Adebanwi, W., (2004a), "The Press and the Politics of Marginal Voices: Narratives of the experiences of the Ogoni of Nigeria", *Media, Culture and Society*, Vol. 26 NO. 6, Sage Publications, London.
- Adebanwi, W., (2004b), *The City, Hegemony and Ethno-Spatial Politics: The Press and the Struggle for Lagos in Colonial Nigeria*", *Nationalism and Ethnic Politics*, 9 (4).
- Adebiyi, B., (2009), "Many Sins of the Media in Nigeria", *The Compass*, Isheri, Ogun State, Nigeria, February 6.
- Agbaje, A.A.B., L., Idowu, A. Agbaje, and A. Layade, (2014, "The Presidency and the Media", in John A.A. Ayoade, Adeoye A. Akinsanya and Olatunde JB Ojo (eds), *The Jonathan Presidency, (The First Year)*, University Press of America, Inc., (UPA),
- Ake, C., (1998), "Governmental instability in Nigeria", *Nigerian Forum*, January-March.
- Akinfeleye, R. A., (2003), "Fourth Estate of the Realm or Fourth Estate of the Wreck: Imperative of Social Responsibility of the Press", being an inaugural lecture delivered at the University of Lagos on Wednesday 14th May.
- Awolowo, O., (1958), 'The Press in the Service of the State', being text of a lecture delivered under the auspices of the Nigeria Union of Journalists, West Nigerian Branch, Ibadan, on 14th June.
- Bankole, Y., (2024), "Naijacracy: How Nigerians defined own democracy in 25 years", *Newspeak*, No. 18 (September), Ibadan, Nigeria.
- Dare, O., (1997), "The Press", in *Transition without End*, edited by Larry Diamond, A. Kirk-Greene and Oyeleye Oyediran, Vantage Publishers, Ibadan, Nigeria.

- Dare, O., (2006), “An Editorial Dilemma”, *The Comet*, (Tuesday), Lagos, May 2.
- Ellis, S., (1989), “Tuning into Pavement Radio”, *African Affairs* Vol. 88 NO. 352 (July).
- Olatubosun, W.A.A., (2024), “Role of Communication and information management in a distressed economy”, being text of a lecture delivered at the 3rd Faculty Lecture series of the Faculty of Communication Science, Lead City University, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria, held on 7th June.
- Ojo, O. E. and P.F. Adebayo, (2013), “Many Sins of the Mass Media in Nigeria: A critical appraisal of the Media in a decade of nascent democracy”, in *Journal of Media and Communication Studies*, Vol. 5 (8), Academic Journals, USA.
- Ojo, O. E., (2003), “Governance and Legitimacy Crisis in Nigeria”, *Research for Development: An International Journal of African Development*, IIXX (1&2) 103-130 (An Official Journal of Nigerian Institute of Social and Economic Research (NISER), Ibadan, Nigeria, (www.niser.org)).
- Ojo, O. E., (2003), “The Mass Media and the Challenges of Sustainable Democratic Values in Nigeria: Possibilities and Limitations”, in *Media, Culture and Society*, Vol. 25, Sage Publications (London), Thousand Oaks and New Delhi.
- Ojo, O. E., (2004), “Public Opinion and the conduct of Nigeria’s Foreign Policy: Two Selected Case Studies”, *The Nigerian Journal of Social Sciences*, III (1) 48-62. An Official Journal of the Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria.
- Ojo, O. E., (2006), “Fourth Estate of the Realm or Wreck: Media, the government and the Nigerian state”, being text of a public lecture delivered at the Kwara State Printing and Publishing

Corporation, publishers of the Herald Newspapers, Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria, 14th June.

- Ojo, O. E., (2013), “Mass Media and Ethnic Politics in Nigeria: An Overview”, in *Studies in Ethnicity and Nationalism*, Vol. 13 No. 3.
- Ojo, O. E., (2018). “Separation of Powers and Good Governance: A Rear View Mirror”, in Ojo, O. E., (ed), *The Legislature and Governance in Nigeria*, (A festschrift for Emeritus Professor John A. A. Ayoade), John Archers (Publishers), Ibadan.
- Ojo, O. E., (ed), (2018), “Separation of Powers and Good Governance: A Rearview Mirror”, in *The Legislature and Governance in Nigeria*, Vol. II. Being a festschrift for Emeritus Professor J.A.A. Ayoade, John Archers Publishers, Ibadan, Nigeria.
- Olukotun, A., (2009), “Media Watchdogs or Partisan Hounds (I)”, *The Compass*, Isheri, Ogun State, Nigeria (March 19).
- Olukotun, A., (2018), “The Media and Democracy in Contemporary Nigeria (Part I), in *Nigerian Compass*, Isheri, Ogun State, Nigeria (October 7).
- Onyeoziri, F., (1982), “The Mass Media as a Political Resource”, (mimeo), Department of Political Science, University of Ibadan, Nigeria - being text of a paper presented at a seminar on ‘The Mass Media and Society, Ibadan, (March).
- Sawant, P.B., (2002), “Mass Media and Democracy: A Global View”, *The Post Express*, Lagos, (Feb. 6).
- Smith, D.J., (2007), “A Culture of Corruption: Everyday Deception and Popular Discontent in Nigeria”, Princeton University Press, Princeton and Oxford.
- Splichae, S., (2002), “The Principle of Publicity, Public Use of Reason and Social Control”, in *Media Culture and Society*, Vol. 24.

- Sunday O., (2008), “Historical context of Media Development” in *Mass Media and Society: A multi-perspective approach*, Ralph Akinfeleye (ed), Department of Mass Communication, University of Lagos.
- Temin, J., and Smith, D.A., (2012), “Media Matters: Evaluating the Role of the Media in Ghana’s 2000 Elections” *African Affairs*, Vol. 101
- Tusa, J., (1992), “Fourth Estate or Fifth Column – Media, the Government and the State”, NIIA Lecture series, A publication of the Nigeria Institute of International Affairs, Lagos, Nigeria.
- Young, C., (1984), “Africa” in Almond G., and Powell, G.B. Jnr. (eds), *Comparative Politics Today, A World View*, Little Brown and Company, Boston.

NEWSPAPERS AND NEWSMAGAZINES

- Newspeak, Ibadan.
Nigerian Compass (Isheri) Ogun State, Nigeria.
Sunday Tribune, Ibadan.
Tell (Lagos)
The Compass, Isheri, Ogun State.
The Post Express (Lagos)